

ISic1181

Apollonia(?) honours Andron son of Thrasios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

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Autopsy

2019-07-23; 2006-04

Last Change

2019-07-23 - Jonathan Prag edited on basis of autopsy in 2006 and 2019

Place of origin (ancient)

Apollonia

Place of origin (modern)

Monte San Fratello

Provenance

First recorded, and still visible, in exterior corner wall of Santuario dei Tre Santi Fratelli, Monte Vecchio, San Fratello (ME)

Coordinates

38.033098, 14.597275

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, San Fratello, Area Archeologica dell'antica Apollonia

Physical Description

A large grey-white limestone block, seemingly intact, in re-use in an external corner wall of a mediaeval church

Dimensions

Height 73 cm

Width 69 cm

Depth 50 cm

Layout

Four lines of Greek text, not quite centred, but lines 2 and 3 fill the width of the face.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain cut letters without serifs, of Hellenistic form. Alpha is straight bar (except possibly broken bar in line 1); beta has two small closed eyes, with a gap between; epsilon has shorter middle bar; the form of theta is unclear (small circle or cross at centre?); kappa has small arms opening from the mid-point of the vertical; mu has curving middle strokes which reach down to the line, but vertical first and last; omicron is generally slightly smaller than the other letters; pi has equal length strokes without overlap; sigma has parallel top and bottom strokes; omega is closed and very slightly elongated, slightly smaller than other letters.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 30-35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. ὁ δᾶμος

2. Ἄνδρωνα(vac.undefinied)Θρασίου Λαλβ

3. εὐεργεσίας ἔνεκεν

4. θεοῖς πᾶσι

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

pietra: ΛΒ

Translation (en)

The people (dedicate) Andron, son of Thrasios, Lab. on account of his good will to all the gods.

Commentary

The text, unusually for Sicily, omits the ethnic of the people erecting the honours for Andron. It is reasonably assumed that the inscription comes from the site of ancient Apollonia, since it has been recorded since the 17th century in re-use in a structural wall of the church of the 'tre santi', which dates back to the 11th/12th century, and within which a number of other pieces of ancient stonework can be seen in re-use also; the church stands within the ancient site. The presence of a demotic abbreviation (to be corrected to 'LAB') finds parallels in a number of other texts from Hellenistic Sicily, and in particular from Halaesa (e.g. ISic0800 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0800>]) and Kaleakte (ISic3628 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3628>]) among nearby sites. The specific abbreviation 'lab' is attested at Halaesa (SEG 59.1100) and in IGDS II.40, a list of names on lead that may come from the area of Siracusa. The presence of identical such abbreviations at, e.g., both Halaesa and Akrai, however, demonstrates that this particular example cannot serve to prove that the text originally came from Halaesa. Dedications 'to all the gods' are also reasonably widespread in Hellenistic Sicily, both at Halaesa and elsewhere. At Halaesa the formula consistently stands at the head of the text, however (e.g. ISic0800 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0800>]); the final position, as here, finds parallels, for instance, at Tauromenion (e.g. ISic3125 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3125>])

Andron [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%91%CE%9D%CE%94%CE%A1%CE%A9%CE%9D] is a reasonably common name, with at least 11 other attestations in Sicily; Thrasios [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%98%CE%A1%CE%91%CE%A3%CE%99%CE%9F%CE%A3] , by contrast, is rare and not attested otherwise in Sicily.

Excavation of ancient Apollonia has to date been limited (see Bonanno 2008), but it is clear that there was a city there in the Hellenistic period and the city is attested in several ancient sources including the Verrines (Cic. 2 Verr. 3.103; 5.86, 90). [<https://topostext.org/place/380146UApo>] .

L. D'Amore 2005 provides a detailed antiquarian/editorial history of the stone's publication, demonstrating that IG XIV.613 of Rhegion is in fact a false doublet deriving from a report of this text.

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